

Supplemental Methods

Study Subjects and Arrays

The study protocol was approved by the UC Davis and UC San Francisco Institutional Review Boards and the University of Alberta Health Research Ethics Board and adheres to all federal and state regulations related to the protection of human research subjects, including The Common Rule, the principles of The Belmont Report, and Institutional policies and procedures that are founded upon ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants or their proxy. Board-certified neurologists diagnosed ICH patients based upon medical histories, exams, and brain imaging. Subjects with Deep ICH had hemorrhages in the basal ganglia, thalamus, cerebellum, and pons/brainstem, while subjects with Lobar ICH had hemorrhages anywhere in the cortex that could extend into adjacent white matter. Blood in the adjacent ventricle may have been present in either location. Controls were matched to stroke location subgroups by vascular risk factors including age, sex, diabetes, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, and race. RNA was isolated and prepared for hybridization as previously described.¹ Quality and purity of the RNA were assessed on a Nanodrop ND-1000 spectrophotometer; RNA integrity was analyzed using the Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer using the ratio of 28S to 18S and RNA Integrity Number (RIN). Total RNA was hybridized on GeneChip® Human Transcriptome Array (HTA) 2.0 (Affymetrix, Santa Clara, CA) to allow for examination of the coding (mRNA) and some of the non-coding human transcriptome, such as precursor (immature) microRNAs species.

Data Processing and Filtering

GC Correction (GCCN) and Single Space Transformation (SST) were applied to the HTA .CEL files using Array Power Tools (APT; Affymetrix) as we previously described.² GCCN-SST transformed .CEL files were then uploaded into Partek Flow software (Partek Inc, St. Louis, MO) where probe sets were mapped to the Human Genome Hg38 using the STAR 2.7.3a aligner and were processed through Partek E/M Quantify to Annotation Model. Nominal read coverage depth was defined as 30 million and default mapping parameters were used. Reads were quantified to the transcriptome (Ensembl Release 102) and RPKM normalized. Genes were then imported into Partek Genomics Suite software (PGS; Partek Inc, St. Louis, MO) for filtering based on expression when divided into Groups (Deep ICH, Lobar ICH, and VRFC). Genes were filtered out of the dataset if they did not have normalized expression values of at least 0.25 in at least 50% of samples in at least one group. This filtered out low expression genes to prevent outliers from driving false positives while retaining genes expressed in only one group. This resulted in a dataset of 23,884 genes.

Differential Expression Analysis

\log_2 (offset 0.0001) transformed expression was modeled by the ANCOVA $Y_{ijk} = \mu + \text{Age} + \text{Group}_i + \text{Sex}_j + \text{Group} * \text{Sex}_{ij} + \epsilon_{ijk}$ where Y is the gene expression, μ is the common effect for the whole experiment; Group is Deep ICH, Lobar ICH, or VRFC; Group*Sex is the interaction between Sex and Group; and ϵ_i is the random error. Contrasts were calculated with Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD).³

ICH Locations

The Lobar ICH vs. VRFC gene list (hereafter referred to as LobarPerGene) was defined as the intersection of the Group-significant genes (Benjamini Hochberg False Discovery Rate (BH) multiple test corrected $p < 0.05$) and the Lobar ICH vs. VRFC contrast significant genes ($p < 0.005$ and Fold-Change $> |1.2|$). The Deep ICH vs. VRFC gene list (hereafter referred to as DeepPerGene) was defined as the intersection of the Group-significant genes (BH corrected $p < 0.05$) and the Deep ICH vs. VRFC contrast significant genes ($p < 0.005$ and Fold-Change $> |1.2|$). The Deep ICH vs. Lobar ICH gene list (hereafter referred to as DeepVsLobar) was defined as the intersection of the Group-significant genes (BH corrected $p < 0.05$) and the Deep ICH vs. Lobar ICH significant genes ($p < 0.005$ and Fold-Change $> |1.2|$).

ICH Location Sex Differences

Sex specific gene lists were selected using modified criteria due to the smaller sample size. Contrasts for the Sex*Group interaction were calculated. These contrasts included Deep ICH Males vs. VRFC Males, Deep ICH Females vs. VRFC Females, Lobar ICH Males vs. VRFC Males, and Lobar ICH Females vs. VRFC Females. Significant differences were defined based upon a $p < 0.005$ and Fold-Change $> |1.2|$ for a given contrast. The gene lists were then compared to the opposite sex for a given location comparison: Deep ICH Males vs. VRFC Males compared to Deep ICH Females vs. VRFC Females; Lobar ICH Males vs. VRFC Males compared to Lobar ICH Females vs. VRFC Females. Genes unique to a specific contrast in these comparisons were selected for downstream biological analysis.

Weighted Gene Co-Expression Network Construction and Analysis

The function *goodSamplesGenes* within the Weighted Gene Co-Expression Network Analysis (WGCNA) package was used to identify missing values or zero-variance genes in the datasets in R.⁴ Both datasets depicted an approximate scale-free topology, as is expected of gene co-expression networks.⁵ Soft-thresholding powers (β) of 14 and 8 were chosen for DeepICHandVRFC and LobarICHandVRFC networks, respectively, to maximize strong correlations between genes while minimizing weak correlations.⁵ WGCNA's signed network function was used to consider both positive and negative correlations.⁶ Due to the large number of genes being processed, the minimum module size was set at 200 genes. The *cutreeDynamic* function was used instead of a static cutoff to form modules due to its adaptability to identify complex dendrograms that allows for identifying nested modules.⁷ Hub genes were defined as

the top 5% of genes per module based on their interconnectivity (kIN—the gene’s intramodular connectivity). These genes represent potential master regulators within their modules.^{8,9} Module associations with Age, Diabetes, Hypertension, Hypercholesterolemia, Sex, and Group were examined independently ($p < 0.05$).

Cell-Specific Gene Involvement

Enrichment with blood cell type-specific genes was identified by overlapping our gene lists and modules with lists of blood cell type-specific genes.^{10,11} Chtanova et al. was used for more comprehensive coverage of T Cell specific genes. Significance of the overlap was quantified using hypergeometric probability testing R function *phyper* with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

Pathway and Gene Ontology Analyses

Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) multiple-comparison adjusted $p < 0.05$ was selected as a significance threshold for both Canonical Pathways and Disease and Function terms generated by IPA. IPA also determined if the significant pathways were activated or inhibited based on the expression direction (fold change) of the input genes using its pathway activity prediction analysis tool. IPA predicts activation/inhibition states of canonical pathways and disease and function terms using its Z-score algorithm, which compared our uploaded datasets and their associated fold changes with the IPA knowledge base’s collection of expression patterns.¹² IPA considers the activation state of key molecules when the Pathway is activated as well as the molecules’ causal relationships with each other and with functional outcomes to calculate the overall prediction. It also generates an activity pattern for the molecules and the end-point functions in the pathway. Canonical pathways with $Z \geq 2$ are predicted significantly activated (referenced hereafter as activated), while ones with $Z \leq -2$ are predicted significantly suppressed (referenced hereafter as suppressed). Similarly, IPA identifies upstream transcriptional regulators that could drive the observed expression patterns in the dataset by searching for enrichment in known targets of the regulators. A Z-score is also calculated for molecules identified as upstream regulators. Molecules with $Z \geq 2$ are considered significantly activated, while ones with $Z \leq -2$ are considered significantly suppressed.¹³ For gene level analyses, ANCOVA model fold changes on Group contrasts (Deep ICH vs. VRFC; Lobar ICH vs. VRFC) were input for activity prediction. For network level analyses, fold changes were calculated with a simple ANOVA on Group with a contrast specific to the desired comparison (Deep ICH vs. VRFC; Lobar ICH vs. VRFC) for all genes within the significant modules.

We used DAVID Functional Annotation Bioinformatics Resources Database to identify enrichment with relevant biological processes (BP), cellular compartments (CC), and molecular functions (MF) with a significance threshold of EASE-adjusted BH $p < 0.05$.^{14,15}

Network Visualization in Cytoscape

The *visantPrepOverall* function was used to generate a list of intramodular gene connections to visualize the module's networks.^{16,17} Parameters *numint=10,000* and *signed=TRUE* were selected. Cytoscape was then used to visualize the networks.^{18,19} For each network, the minimum weight cutoff was adjusted to ensure the number of nodes and connections were visually distinguishable. Nodes representing cell-type specific genes were colored based on their cell-type and were given labels. Nodes representing hub genes were made larger and given large labels. Edge lengths were arbitrary.

Supplemental Discussion

Due to the length of the discussion in the main manuscript, we present additional discussion of this study's findings in this Supplement.

Blood Cell Response to ICH

Dendritic Cells in Deep and Lobar ICH

Dendritic cells are antigen presenting cells forming the interface between the innate and adaptive immune systems. They degrade proteins into peptides and present them as antigens to T and B Cells, and produce cytokines for T Cell activation.²⁰ In an ICH mouse model, they infiltrated the brain 12 hours after hemorrhage onset.²¹ In this study, Dendritic Cell Maturation was a common significant pathway to both ICH locations, such as in DC-Grey60 (activated), DeepPerGene, LC-RoyalBlue (suppressed), LC-DarkGreen (activated), and LobarPerGene (activated). DeepVsLobar's member *TAB1* is involved in TNF signaling in dendritic cells, where it activates MAPK14²² and increases expression of various surface receptors and CD proteins. *MAPK14*, which was also present in our data in the DeepPerGene list and in the LobarPerGenelist, plays a role in regulation of pro- and anti-inflammatory signaling in myeloid cells,²³ potentially through Toll-Like Receptor (TLR) regulation.²⁴ Six TLRs were common between ICH locations; *TLR2* and *TLR4* (involved in Dendritic Cell Maturation) had positive fold changes. In Dendritic Cells, TLRs induce pro-inflammatory cytokine production and T Cell stimulation.²⁵ DeepPerGene, LC-RoyalBlue and LobarPerGene were all significant for the Communication between Innate and Adaptive Immune Cells pathway, which includes Dendritic Cell stimulation of B and T Cells. In LC-RoyalBlue, *CCR7*, *HLA-DOA* (an MHC II subunit), *PIK3R1*, and *ELP1* (an IKK subunit) all had decreased expression in ICH patients. *CCR7* is involved in dendritic cell migration²⁶ and MHC complexes are involved in antigen presentation.²⁷ Though both Deep and Lobar ICH had modules where Dendritic Cell Maturation was activated, the additional module in Lobar ICH (LC-RoyalBlue) where Dendritic Cell Maturation was suppressed underscores potential differences in this pathway between ICH locations.

Natural Killer and Natural Killer T Cell Response

Natural Killer T (NKT) Cells are a subset of T Lymphocytes that express TCR and NK Cell surface markers.^{28,29} They respond to glycolipids like LPS, producing inflammatory cytokines and influencing the response of other immune cells.²⁸ Though little is known about the NKT response to ICH, studies have shown their response to ischemic stroke, potentially preventing infections.³⁰ DeepVsLobar genes *TRAF3* and *CD226* (both downregulated in Deep vs. Lobar ICH) are involved in many NKT functions like Frequency of iNKT1 Cells, Frequency of iNKT2 Cells, Development of Invariant Natural Killer T Cells, Proliferation of Invariant Natural Killer T Cells, and Survival of Invariant Natural Killer T Cells. This gives evidence for potential differences in the NKT response to ICH based on Location. Indeed, Deep ICH gene lists were enriched in functions Development of Natural Killer T Lymphocytes (all genes downregulated in Deep ICH vs. VRFC) and Quantity of Natural Killer T Lymphocytes (downregulated with non-significant $Z = -0.89$), implicating a potential downregulated NKT response to Deep hemorrhages. Lobar ICH gene lists were enriched in Apoptosis of Invariant Natural Killer T Cells and Arrest in Development of Invariant Natural Killer T Cells with gene *FNIP1* upregulated in Lobar ICH vs. VRFC. This could reduce apoptosis of iNKT cells³¹ as FNIP1 is required for NKT development and survival.³¹⁻³³ Together, these results show a potential upregulation of NKT cell related pathways in Lobar ICH and a downregulation in Deep ICH. In mice, iNKT modulation (with α -galactosylceramide) was protective against infection after ischemic stroke by shifting production of cytokines from anti-inflammatory IL-10 to pro-inflammatory molecules.³⁴ In human ischemic stroke, increased levels of IL-10 were associated with patients with worse outcomes and infections.³⁵ A study of infection after human ICH found an increased risk of infection in Deep ICH compared to Lobar ICH (OR: 1.9; 95% CI: 1.28–2.88).³⁶ This difference may be associated with differential NKT cell activity, which may be a Deep ICH specific therapeutic target for preventing infection.

Little is known about the Natural Killer (NK) cell response to ICH. They produce cytokines and have cytotoxic functions.³⁷ One study showed minimal NK cell infiltration into the CNS after ICH,³⁸ while another showed prominent infiltration in human patients who underwent early hematoma evacuation.³⁹ Another group found decreased numbers of peripheral NK cells 3 and 14 days after ICH compared to controls.⁴⁰ In a previous study, we found a module of ICH associated genes enriched in NK cell specific genes.² In this study, DC-Grey60, DeepPerGene, LC-DarkGreen and LC-Pink were significant for Natural Killer Cell Signaling, with all but DeepPerGene activated. *CD226* (in DeepPerGene and LC-RoyalBlue) is a cell surface receptor in the Natural Killer Cell Receptor Signaling pathway. It is involved in NK cell function and regulation of dendritic cells.⁴¹ *CD226* is also a DeepVsLobar gene, implicating different NK cell response mechanisms between ICH locations. This was reinforced by Deep but not Lobar ICH enrichment in other NK cell related functions. These included NK Cell Proliferation, Activation of Natural Killer Cells, Cytolysis of Natural Killer Cells, and Production of Natural Killer Precursor Cells. Though both locations were enriched in NK cell receptor signaling, these results show potential differences in the molecular responses of NK cells depending on hemorrhage location.

B Cell Response

The B Cell response to ICH is also poorly characterized.^{42,43} B Cells are involved in cytokine production, pro- and anti-inflammatory signaling, and neuronal survival signaling, and may be involved in pre/post ischemic stroke neuroprotection.⁴⁴ There is minimal B Cell infiltration into the CNS after ICH³⁸ and a reduction of B Cells in peripheral blood after ICH.⁴⁰ We have previously shown peripheral differential expression of B Cell Signaling genes in ICH compared to control^{1,2} and with respect to ICH and perihematomal edema volumes.⁴⁵ In this study, B Cell Receptor Signaling was significant in DC-Grey60 (activated), DeepPerGene, LC-DarkGreen (activated), LC-Pink (activated), and LC-Pink Hubs. Additionally, both Deep and Lobar ICH had modules significant for the function Quantity of B Lymphocytes, activated in DC-Grey60 and LC-Pink modules. This gives additional evidence that B Cells are potentially involved in the human ICH response in both ICH locations.

Erythroblast Response

Erythroblasts are immature nucleated red blood cells (NRBC) which mature into red blood cells (RBC).⁴⁶ They can be found in peripheral blood after large hemorrhages, inflammation, and hypoxia⁴⁷ and elevated peripheral NRBCs is associated with worse outcomes.⁴⁸ NRBCs may be able to respond to viral PAMPs (pathogen-associated molecular patterns) through TLR signaling pathways. CNS hemorrhages in preterm neonates and growth-restricted infants are also associated with elevated NRBC levels.^{49,50} We have previously shown erythroblast-specific differential gene expression peripheral blood following human ICH.^{2,45} In this study, LC-Black was enriched in Erythroblast cell type specific genes. Lobar ICH enrichment included Differentiation of Erythroblasts (LC-Black Hubs), Quantity of Erythroid Precursor Cells (LC-Black activated and LC-Black Hubs), Erythrocyte Differentiation (LC-Black), and Differentiation of Erythroid Cells (LC-Black and LC-DarkGreen). There was minimal involvement of Deep ICH lists in erythroid cell-related pathways, and no Deep ICH enrichment in erythroblast gene lists, pathways, functions, or GO terms. The growth factor pathway Erythropoietin Signaling was significant in DC-Grey60, DeepPerGene, and LC-DarkGreen. Erythropoietin regulates RBC generation.⁴⁶ Increased RBC generation through erythropoiesis may improve outcomes,⁵¹ though this is debated.⁵² Further studies are needed to elucidate the role of erythroblasts in ICH of different locations.

Inflammatory Signaling

Cytokine Signaling

After ICH, a large number of cytokines are released, and pro-inflammatory cytokine signaling likely contributes to secondary injury by compromising the blood-brain barrier (BBB) thus allowing for additional edema formation and immune cell invasion.^{42,53} In this study, many cytokine signaling pathways were overrepresented in both Deep and Lobar ICH lists (Figure 3A), such as pro-inflammatory IL-17, IL-23, TNFR1, TNFR2, and IL-1 Signaling⁵³ and anti-inflammatory IL-4, IL-10, and TGF- β Signaling.⁵³ Activated peripheral blood cells release cytokine TNF- α after stroke,⁵⁴ beginning a pro-inflammatory signaling pathway through TNFR1

and TNFR2 in ICH.⁵³ *TNFRSF10B* (LC-DarkGreen) and *TNFRSF10C* (DC-Grey60 and LC-Pink) are receptors for *TNFSF10* (aka TRAIL; DC-LightGreen, DeepPerGene, and LC-GGrey60), another TNF family ligand. TRAIL signaling is implicated in neuronal apoptosis after TBI⁵⁵ and blocking TRAIL-DR5 interactions improved long term neuron survival in a mouse cerebral ischemia model.⁵⁶ *TNFSF13B* (aka BAFF), present in DC-LightGreen and LC-Grey60, is a B cell activator involved in their differentiation and replication.⁵⁷ Transcripts for 3 TNF- α induced proteins were also members of ICH-location significant modules: *TNFAIP6* in DC-LightGreen and LC-Grey60, *TNFAIP8* in LC-Grey60, and *TNFAIP8L2* in DC-LightGreen. TNF Receptor associated protein coding genes *TRAF1*, *TRAF3*, and *TRAF5* were present in Deep lists but not Lobar lists. In addition, IL-1B signaling genes were also present in the Location-significant modules for both Lobar and Deep ICH. *IL1B* was present in DC-Grey60 and LC-Pink. IL-1B is a strong pro-inflammatory mediator secreted by neurons, microglia, and astrocytes; monocytes responding to the hemorrhage may also increase IL-1B levels.⁵³ *IL1R1* (IL-1 Receptor 1; present in DC-Grey60 and hub in LC-Pink), *IL1R2* (IL-1 Receptor 2; DC-Grey60 and LC-Pink), *IL1RAP* (Interleukin 1 Receptor Accessory Protein; DC-Grey60 and LC-Pink), and *IL1RN* (Interleukin 1 Receptor Antagonist; DC-LightGreen) were also present. *IL18* (LC-Grey60) is another pro-inflammatory cytokine activated by the NLRP3 Inflammasome.⁵³ IL-18 increases in hypoxic-ischemia in rats and may contribute to brain injury.⁵⁸ Also present were *IL18BP* (Interleukin 18 Binding Protein; LC-RoyalBlue), *IL18R1* (Interleukin 18 Receptor 1; DC-LightGreen, DeepPerGene, and LC-Pink), and *IL18RAP* (Interleukin 18 Receptor Accessory Protein; DC-Grey60 and LC-Pink). Receptors for two anti-inflammatory interleukins were also common: *IL4R* (Interleukin 4 Receptor) was present in DC-Grey60, DeepPerGene, and LC-Pink while *IL10RB* (Interleukin 10 Receptor Subunit Beta) was present in DC-Grey60 and LobarPerGene. IL-4 inhibits the inflammatory response while contributing to differentiation into anti-inflammatory Th2 type T helper cells and M2 type microglial cells.⁵³ In a rat ICH model, injection of IL-4 induced a shift to M2 type response and decreased neural deficits.⁵⁹ In mice, IL-4 treatment improved recovery and hematoma resolution.⁶⁰ IL-10 also contributes to Th1/Th2 balance, inhibits TNF production in macrophages, and generally contributes to anti-inflammatory signaling.⁵³ IL-10 associates with outcomes and could act as a biomarker of long term outcomes for ICH patients.⁶¹ *TGFBR1* (Transforming Growth Factor Beta Receptor 3) and *TGFBR3* (Transforming Growth Factor Beta Receptor 3) were both present in DeepPerGene. TGF- β contributes to Treg cell proliferation and brain repair.⁵³ Early TGF- β increases are associated with improved 90-day outcomes in human patients⁶² and as such is a potential treatment target. The balance between these pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines likely contributes to the damage-repair processes after ICH regardless of location, and modulation of this system might modulate outcomes.

Growth Factor Signaling

Growth factors (GF) play a role in brain recovery after ICH. Indeed, higher serum levels of various growth factors were associated with better mRS outcomes in human ICH patients at 3 months.^{63,64} In this study, many GF signaling pathways were common to Deep and Lobar ICH. The ErbB Signaling pathway was common to both locations (DC-Grey60 activated, DeepPerGene, LC-DarkGreen activated, LC-Pink Hubs), as were sub-pathways ErbB2-ErbB3 Signaling (DC-Grey60 activated, LC-DarkGreen) and ErbB4 Signaling (DC-Grey60 activated,

DeepPerGene, LC-DarkGreen activated, and LC-Pink Hubs). In addition, in this study, Neuregulin Signaling (DC-Grey60, DeepPerGene, LC-Pink activated, and LC-DarkGreen) and Endocannabinoid Developing Neuron Pathway (DC-Grey60 activated, LC-Black suppressed, LC-DarkGreen activated, and LC-Pink activated) were also common between locations. Neuregulin-1 (aka NRG1) signaling through ErbB4 receptors protected against BBB disruption after SAH⁶⁵ and promoted recovery after TBI⁶⁶ in rodent models. NRG-1 was associated with neuroprotection in rodent models of IS⁶⁷⁻⁶⁹ and may induce oligodendrocyte precursor proliferation to attenuate injury after ICH.⁷⁰ Though many preclinical studies have been performed to research the role of endocannabinoids as an IS therapy, their utility is still unclear.⁷¹ In ICH, a rat model showed treatment with a cannabinoid receptor 2 agonist was able to reduce BBB breakdown.⁷² Another common pathway, Erythropoietin Signaling, was significant in DC-Grey60 (activated), DeepPerGene, and LC-DarkGreen (activated). Erythropoietin promotes the differentiation and division of RBC,⁷³ and was neuroprotective after ICH in animal models.⁷⁴⁻⁷⁷ FGF Signaling was significant in DeepPerGene and LC-DarkGreen (activated). Elevated FGF23 is a risk factor for ICH but not IS,⁷⁸ and protected the BBB after ICH in mouse models.⁷⁹ Growth Hormone Signaling was also common (DC-Grey60 activated, DeepPerGene, and LC-Pink). One study showed higher levels of Growth Hormone in ICH patients with worse outcomes and in those who died within 30 days.⁸⁰ Insulin-Like Growth Factor (IGF-1) Signaling was significant in DC-Grey60 (activated), DeepPerGene, and LC-DarkGreen (activated). IGF-1 is neuroprotective in rat IS⁸¹ and mouse ICH.⁸² Insulin-Like Growth Factor 1 Receptor (*IGF1R*) was an LC-Pink member and was found increased in ICH. IL-7 Signaling was significant in DC-Grey60 (activated), DeepPerGene, LC-Black (suppressed), LC-DarkGreen (activated), LC-Pink (activated) and LC-Pink Hubs. IL-7 is involved in the development, maintenance, and survival of all T Cell subtypes.⁸³ NGF Signaling was common to both locations (DeepPerGene; both LC-DarkGreen and LC-Pink activated). Treatment with mouse NGF improved outcomes in adult⁸⁴ and neonatal⁸⁵ human ICH subjects. Other GF pathways including GM-CSF Signaling and HGF Signaling were common between locations (*HGF* was a DC-LightGreen hub, though the module was not significant for the pathway).

Intracellular Signaling

Many intracellular signaling pathways are either regulated by or contribute to the production of cytokines in response to insults like hemorrhagic stroke. TLRs can be expressed on neural and glial cells and can activate the production of pro-inflammatory molecules.⁸⁶ Specifically, TLR4 is involved in inflammatory phagocytosis after ICH.⁸⁷ Toll-Like Receptor Signaling was found significant in DC-Grey60 (activated), DeepPerGene (activated), LC-DarkGreen (activated), LC-Pink (activated with hub MAPK14), and LobarPerGene. A total of 7 TLRs (*TLR1,2,4,5,6,8,10*) were present in our gene lists; *TLR10* was unique to LC-Pink while all others were common to Deep and Lobar ICH. TLR4 (DC-Grey60, DeepPerGene, LC-DarkGreen) responds to extracellular Danger-associated molecular patterns (DAMPs) including HMGB1, heme, thrombin, and fibrin.^{42,43} ICH results in death and lysis of RBC, releasing hemoglobin (and thus heme) into the hematoma and perihematoma regions.⁸⁸ Additionally, the HMGB1 Signaling pathway was common between locations and was significant for DC-Grey60 (trend towards activation with $Z = 1.67$), DeepPerGene, LC-Pink (activated) and LC-Pink Hubs. These among other ICH induced signals activate TLR receptors and consequently begin

signaling cascades including p38 MAPK Signaling and NF- κ B Signaling Pathways. Both MAPK and NF- κ B are involved in inflammatory and immune signaling.⁸⁹ The p38 MAPK Signaling Pathway was significant in DC-Grey60, DC-LightGreen, DeepPerGene (activated), and LC-Pink (activated). The p38 MAPK pathway is involved in inflammatory cytokine production and apoptosis signaling.⁹⁰ Activation of p38 induces production of pro-inflammatory cytokines like IL-1, IL-6, and TNF- α .⁹⁰ In a rat ischemic stroke model, p38 inhibition was neuroprotective,⁹¹ making it a potential treatment target.⁹² Propagermanium reduced edema and improved function in ICH rats, potentially through CCL2-p38 MAPK inhibition.⁹³ *TAB1* (TGF-Beta Activated Kinase 1 (MAP3K7) Binding Protein 1) was a member of DeepVsLobar and was higher in Lobar ICH. Disrupting TAB1 involvement in p38 signaling could reduce MAPK induced pro inflammatory signaling.⁹⁴ NF- κ B is a transcription factor responsible for modulation of gene expression in response to environmental stimuli.⁹⁵ It is highly expressed after ICH and regulates the expression of various inflammatory cytokines and HO-1, among other genes.⁹⁵ The NF- κ B Signaling pathway was common to both locations, and was significant in DC-Grey60 (activated), DeepPerGene, LC-DarkGreen (activated), LC-Pink (activated), and LobarPerGene. *NFKB1* (Nuclear Factor Kappa B Subunit 1) was a member of LC-Pink, and NF- κ B inhibitors *NFKBIA* (aka I κ B α) and *NFKBIZ* (aka I κ B ζ) were common between locations. I κ B binds to NF- κ B, thus inhibiting it. Phosphorylation and ubiquitination leads to dissociation of the two and degradation of the inhibitor.⁹⁶ Slowing this degradation of inhibitors may be a potential target for treatments. A large number of small molecules are known to target the NF- κ B pathway, but few have been examined in ICH.⁹⁶ One such small molecule, antioxidant ethyl pyruvate, was neuroprotective and reduced inflammation in an ICH mouse model.⁹⁷ However, more research is needed on NF- κ B inhibitors in response to both Deep and Lobar ICH. The pathway Role of NFAT in Regulation of the Immune Response was also common between locations, and was significant in DC-Grey60 (activated), DeepPerGene, LC-DarkGreen (activated), LC-Pink (activated), LC-RoyalBlue, and LobarPerGene. NFAT family transcription factors regulate expression of T Cell activation and development genes in response to T Cell Receptor stimulation.⁹⁸ They modulate the expression of some of the genes targeted by the above intracellular signaling cascades. *NFATC2* (aka *NFAT1*) and *NFATC3* (AKA *NFAT4*) are DeepPerGene members implicated in the proportion of Th1 and Th2 cells⁹⁸ which could modulate damage and repair after ICH. NFAT proteins expressed in ischemic neurons may also contribute to IL-4 production, thus driving microglia to a restorative M2 phenotype.⁹⁹ As such, NFAT expression could be a therapeutic anti-inflammatory target after ICH. These intracellular signaling pathways play a significant role in immune and inflammatory responses to both Deep and Lobar hemorrhages and are a common response to ICH.

CREB in ICH

cAMP-response-element binding protein (CREB) is a transcription factor that induces the transcription of GFs, neurotransmitters, and intracellular signaling molecules. These targets are involved in neural protection and plasticity.¹⁰⁰ In ischemic stroke animal models, CREB potentiates functional recovery¹⁰¹ and in ICH, CREB suppresses neuroinflammation.¹⁰² In this study, the CREB Signaling in Neurons pathway was activated in Deep ICH, though two CREB-related genes were associated with Lobar ICH. Thus, CREB likely plays a role in Deep and Lobar ICH.

Blood Vessel Formation

Angiogenesis describes the expansion of the vascular system from existing vessels. Vasculogenesis describes the *de novo* creation of new vessels.¹⁰³ Angiogenesis occurs in response to ischemic stroke,¹⁰⁴ and rat models of ICH show evidence of cerebral angiogenesis.¹⁰⁵ The exact role of vessel formation after stroke is debated - some argue it can improve outcomes,¹⁰⁶ while others argue that angiogenesis-inducing factors are detrimental as they can also increase edema formation.¹⁰⁷ In this study, Deep and Lobar ICH gene lists were enriched in angiogenesis and vasculogenesis functions. These included Angiogenesis (in DC-LightGreen, DC-LightGreen Hubs, and activated in LC-Pink), Angiogenesis of Brain (in DC-Grey60 Hubs and DC-LightGreen Hubs), and Vasculogenesis (in DC-LightGreen and DC-LightGreen Hubs). LC-Pink was also significantly enriched in Inhibition of Angiogenesis by TSP1. The Angiopoietin Signaling Pathway was common between locations, with DeepPerGene and LC-Pink significantly enriched. Angiopoietins are ligands for TIE1 and TIE2, vascular endothelial cell tyrosine kinase receptors involved in angiogenesis.¹⁰⁸ Similarly, other signaling pathways common between locations are implicated in angiogenesis, some of which were activated. These include HGF Signaling,¹⁰⁹ HIF1 α Signaling,^{110,111} FAK Signaling,¹¹² Apelin Endothelial Signaling Pathway,¹¹³ and PDGF Signaling.¹¹⁴ The role of these pathways in the recovery from ICH requires further study to determine whether they would be important treatment targets.

Cell Death

Apoptosis in ICH

Cell death pathways (including apoptosis) can contribute to neurological deficits after ICH.¹¹⁵⁻¹¹⁷ In this study, the function Apoptosis was common between locations and significant in DC-Grey60 (suppressed), DC-LightGreen, DeepPerGene (trend towards activation, $Z = 1.67$), LC-Black (activated), LC-DarkGreen, LC-Grey60 (trend towards suppression, $Z = -1.78$), LC-Pink (trend towards suppression, $Z = -1.84$), LC-RoyalBlue Hubs (trend towards activation, $Z = 1.87$), and LobarPerGene. LC-DarkGreen, LC-Pink, and LobarPerGene were significant for the Apoptosis Signaling Pathway. Many other apoptosis pathways and functions were present in both locations. Apoptosis induced by hemorrhagic products like ROS and thrombin is reported in ICH animal models.^{116,118} Caspase 3 (*CASP3*), an LC-Grey60 member, is a neuronal apoptosis executioner.^{116,119} *CASP1*, *CASP4*, and *CASP5* were common between locations and are involved in inflammatory regulation.¹¹⁹ BCL-2 family genes (present in Deep and Lobar ICH lists) are regulators of intrinsic apoptosis pathways and may interact with some caspases.^{116,120} They included *BCL2L11* (aka BIM; pro-apoptotic; in DC-LightGreen),¹²¹ *BCL2L13* (aka BCL-RAMBO; pro-apoptotic; in LC-Black),¹²² *BCL2L1* (anti-apoptotic; in LC-Black),^{123,124} and *BCL2A1* (anti-apoptotic; in DC-LightGreen, DeepPerGene, LC-Grey60, and LobarPerGene).¹²⁵ *BCL2A1* promotes the survival of specific leukocytes.¹²⁵ Other B-Cell Lymphoma genes included *BCL10* (pro-apoptotic; in DC-Grey60 and DeepPerGene and hub in LC-DarkGreen)¹²⁶⁻¹²⁸ and *BCL6* (anti-apoptotic; in DC-Grey60 and hub in LC-Pink).^{129,130} *BCL10* induces apoptosis and activates the NF- κ B pathway,¹²⁶⁻¹²⁸ though its effectiveness is debated.¹²⁷ In our data, Apoptosis is

suggested to be suppressed in some, while activated in other modules/gene lists in both Deep and Lobar ICH, indicating complex regulation of apoptosis, with some common and some specific genes involved in both ICH locations.

Protein Processing Pathways Are Unique to Lobar ICH

Ubiquitin-Like Modifications

Protein SUMOylation is a reversible post-translational modification (using SUMOs, or small ubiquitin-like modifiers) that changes protein interaction surfaces, modifying protein stability and activity.¹³¹ SUMOylation plays a role in inflammatory responses,^{132,133} potentially through NF- κ B and TLR signaling,¹³³ in T Cell activation,¹³² and Treg activity.¹³³ SUMOylation plays a role in neuroprotection after cerebral ischemia / ischemic stroke in mice and rats,^{134,135} though little is known about its role in ICH. We previously found that an ICH module was enriched in protein SUMOylation genes.² In this study one Lobar ICH module was significant for the SUMOylation Pathway, but none in Deep ICH. Lobar ICH associated with SUMO protein coding genes *SUMO1* and *SUMO4*. These SUMO proteins are activated by an E1 enzyme, transferred to an E2 enzyme like *UBE2I* (also associated with Lobar ICH), and attached to the final substrate / target proteins with the assistance of E3 enzymes.¹³⁶ Additionally, *SUMO1P3*, also associated with Lobar ICH, is implicated in proliferation and migration in cancer subtypes as an oncogene.¹³⁷⁻¹³⁹ *NEDD4L*, a NEDD4 family E3 enzyme,¹⁴⁰ also associated with Lobar ICH. *NEDD4L* deletion worsens outcomes in ischemic stroke mouse models.¹⁴¹ These combined results implicate alterations in SUMOylation and NEDDylation as potential Lobar ICH treatment targets.

Enrichment in RNA Processing, Trafficking, Splicing, and Degradation is Lobar ICH-Specific

Splicing dysfunction is associated with many diseases, and the minor spliceosome is implicated in stress-induced gene expression regulation.¹⁴² We have previously shown differential alternative splicing in ICH^{1,143} and have found enrichment in alternative splicing processes at the gene and network level in ICH.^{2,45} Here, we found enrichment in various RNA processing, splicing, and degradation processes in Lobar but not Deep ICH, implicating potential differences based on ICH location. LC-RoyalBlue was found significantly enriched in GO terms RNA Processing, RNA Binding, ATP-dependent RNA helicase activity, poly(A) RNA Binding and function term Processing of RNA. LC-RoyalBlue Hubs were significantly enriched in functions Binding of RNA Fragment, Deadenylation of mRNA, Deadenylation of mRNA Fragment, Destabilization of mRNA, Localization of mRNA, Metabolism of RNA, Repression of mRNA, Splicing of hnRNA, and Splicing of RNA. LC-Black, a module where the eigengene was down-regulated in Lobar ICH vs. VRFC, was significantly enriched in Inhibition of ARE-Mediated mRNA Degradation Pathway. No RNA processing or splicing terms were significant for any of the Deep ICH lists. LC-RoyalBlue, another module where the eigengene was down-regulated in Lobar ICH vs. VRFC, had 8 nucleotide helicases (*MCM3* (hub), *DDX19A*, *DDX5*, *DHX9*, *G3BP1*

(hub), *DHX36*, *DDX21*, and *DHX29*). RNA Helicases are enzymes involved in trafficking mRNA between processing areas of the cell, removing them from the pool of actively translated transcripts,¹⁴⁴ and transcriptional regulation.¹⁴⁵⁻¹⁴⁸ G3BP1 can trigger formation of stress granules (a form of ribonucleoprotein (RNP) granules), which are RNA-protein assemblies, in response to cellular stress.¹⁴⁵ DHX9 is involved not only in RNA processing and trafficking but also in DNA replication regulation.¹⁴⁷ DDX5 cooperates with hnRNPs to regulate splicing. It also regulates expression of genes involved in cell differentiation.¹⁴⁶ hnRNP family proteins work cooperatively on RNA processing and splicing functions.¹⁴⁹ *HNRNPH1* (LC-RoyalBlue Hub) regulates gene splicing.^{150,151} Some of its target genes are involved in splicing, MAPK Signaling, and Ubiquitin Mediated Proteolysis.¹⁵¹ Another LC-RoyalBlue hub *SYNCRIP* (aka *HNRNPQ*) is linked to splicing with *HNRNPR* (also an LC-RoyalBlue member).^{150,152,153} LC-RoyalBlue Hub *TARDBP* is a paralog of *SYNCRIP* that plays a role in splicing.¹⁵⁴ It splices autophagy related genes¹⁵⁵ and is involved in cellular stress granule response and RNA storage.¹⁵⁶ LC-RoyalBlue also contained *HNRNPA1* pseudogenes (as currently annotated), *HNRNPH1* pseudogenes, *TARDBP* pseudogenes, and a *HNRNPR* pseudogene. Though little is known about pseudogene function, some can be processed into short interfering RNAs and can modulate transcription or translation through RNA interference,¹⁵⁷ thus forming another potential mechanism by which LC-RoyalBlue regulates RNA. Thus, Lobar ICH was found to be enriched in many RNA processing, trafficking, and splicing pathways that were not found in Deep ICH. These processes were enriched in the two modules (LC-RoyalBlue and LC-Black), where genes were downregulated in Lobar ICH vs. Control. Moreover, LC-RoyalBlue had no significant overlap with either of the two Deep ICH modules, signifying it is highly Lobar-specific module. Though it is likely splicing plays a role in Deep ICH, these results point to potential differential alternative splicing between ICH locations. Transcript- or alternative splicing-level analyses could unveil additional differences between Deep and Lobar ICH responses.

Sex Differences in Immune Response to Deep and Lobar Hemorrhages

Sex differences in the human immune and inflammatory systems are well characterized. These include TLR pathways, immunoglobulin activity, and leukocyte counts and production.¹⁵⁸ Male ICH subjects also have higher rates of hematoma expansion¹⁵⁹ and higher 90 day mortality rates^{159,160} than females. Additionally, sex differences exist in peripheral blood gene expression in healthy subjects,¹⁶¹ emphasizing the importance of sex as a factor in transcriptomic studies. Though we have previously shown transcriptome level sex differences in Ischemic Stroke (IS),¹⁶²⁻¹⁶⁶ sex differences in the ICH transcriptome are not well characterized. To further our understanding of how sex impacts patient responses to ICH, we conducted a pilot analysis on sex differences in Deep and Lobar ICH.

Male ICH Response

Male-DvC (Male-Deep ICH vs. Male-Control) and Male-LvC (Male-Lobar ICH vs. Male-Control) lists had minimal enrichment in pathways, functions or terms and no enrichment in cell-type specific lists. Male-DvC was enriched in the Apelin Liver Signaling and DNA Methylation

and Transcriptional Repression Signaling pathways as well as functions Gene Silencing, Sprouting Angiogenesis, Stabilization of Synapse, and Activation-induced cell death of CD4+ T-lymphocytes. Male-LvC was not enriched in any pathways or functions. Of the 27 Male-DvC genes, 3 were miRNA (*MIR19A*, *MIR495*, and *MIR4777*) which were all upregulated in Deep ICH vs. VRFC. Inhibition of mature *MIR19A* was neuroprotective in preclinical IS studies¹⁶⁷⁻¹⁶⁹ and could play a similar role after ICH. In mice, inhibition of mature *MIR495* miRNA promoted vascularization and blood flow recovery after IS.¹⁷⁰ Another Male-DvC member, Endothelin 2 (*EDN2*), is a pro-inflammatory chemoattractant of neutrophils and macrophages.¹⁷¹ A variable-region T Cell receptor subunit, *TRBV29-1*, was also present in Male-DvC. Male-LvC was significant for the GO term Protein Binding. Male-DvC was not significant for any GO terms. Male-LvC genes *NRF2*, *DNAJB11*, *MAP3K1*, and *NQO2* are involved in the NRF2-Mediated Oxidative Stress Response pathway. No Male-DvC genes were involved in the pathway. *CD48* was present in Male-LvC. It is highly expressed in B and T cells.¹⁷² *CD48*, *KIR2DL4*, and *MAP3K1*, involved in the NK Cell Signaling pathway, were differentially expressed in Male-LvC. Male-LvC also had 6 peptidase encoding genes upregulated, including *HTRA2*, *PSMA6*, *SPPL2A*, *TMEM59*, *UFD1*, and *ZMPSTE24*. *HTRA2* cleaves APP, preventing mitochondrial accumulation and inhibiting the ability of A β plaques to form.¹⁷³ *SPPL2A* is implicated in AD risk, and cleaves proteins involved in neurodegeneration and immune system function.¹⁷⁴ *TMEM59* is involved in APP shedding and downregulates A β formation by inhibiting α - and β -secretase activity on the precursor protein.¹⁷⁵

Female ICH Response

Female-DvC (Female-Deep ICH vs. Female-Control) and Female-LvC (Female-Lobar ICH vs. Female-Control) lists were both highly enriched in various immune and inflammatory pathways already discussed. Both were significantly enriched in Neutrophil, T Cell, and T Cell Receptor and Signaling specific gene lists. In healthy patients, these immune cell types tend to have higher count and phagocytic ability in Females.¹⁵⁸ Female-DvC was enriched in GF signaling pathways ErbB4, GM-CSF, Growth Hormone, HGF, IL-7, Neuregulin, NGF, and PDGF Signaling. Female-LvC had no significant enrichment in GF signaling pathways. Common cytokine pathways included TREM1 Signaling (activated in Deep and Lobar ICH), Regulation of IL-2 Expression in Activated and Anergic T Lymphocytes (suppressed in both), T Helper Cell Differentiation, Th1 Pathway, Th2 Pathway, Th1 and Th2 Activation Pathway, Dendritic Cell Maturation, CCR3 Signaling in Eosinophils, and CCR5 Signaling in Macrophages. Pathways for IL-(1,2,3,22) Signaling, Inflammasome (activated), Chemokine Signaling, HMGB1 Signaling, and GO term Apoptotic Process were unique to Female-DvC. GM-CSF, IL-2, IL-3, and IL-7 are all involved in regulation of the adaptive immune system,¹⁷⁶ giving more evidence for changes in T and B Cell behavior after both Deep and Lobar ICH in Females. Also common to both locations were T Cell Receptor Signaling (suppressed in both), B Cell Receptor Signaling, Natural Killer Cell Signaling, fMLP Signaling in Neutrophils, and Leukocyte Extravasation Signaling. 4-1BB Signaling in T Lymphocytes, Endocannabinoid Cancer Inhibition Pathway, Response to Lipopolysaccharide, Positive Regulation of IL-4, and MyD88-dependent toll-like receptor signaling pathway were unique to Female-LvC. NF- κ B Signaling, TLR Signaling (activated in both), Neuroinflammation Signaling (activated in both), and iNOS Signaling (activated in both) were other common pathways important for the human immune response to

ICH. These results are similar to our findings in Ischemic Stroke where Female differentially expressed genes were enriched in a number of immune and inflammatory pathways and GO terms.¹⁶²⁻¹⁶⁴

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